

LIVESTOCK TRADITIONS AND CEREMONIES
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF JIZZAKH OASIS)

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t.f.d. prof.: Doniyorov Alisher Xudayberdievich
Professor of Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies,
Eshmuhamatov Akhror Sharipovich
Basic doctoral student of
Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies.

Summary: *This article is based on the results of archaeological research in the Jizzakh oasis, which has long been used by the population due to its natural geographical position and favorable climatic conditions for animal husbandry. Field ethnographic materials also show that many customs, rituals, traditions and specific professional values were formed as a result of careful attitude to livestock products and their species, which are important in the daily life of the people of the oasis.*

Key words: *Morguzar, Nurata, Mirzachul, Gulbo, Saganok, Bekkeldi, Kamish, Pardakulteпа, Komilboboteпа, Saikhonsai, Takatosh, Suzmoylota, Farn, Shepherd’s staff, Lame father, Bely, “flock joining”.*

**ЧОРВАЧИЛИК БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ УРФ–ОДАТ ВА МАРОСИМЛАР (ЖИЗЗАХ
ВОҲАСИ МИСОЛИДА)**

т.ф.д. проф.: Дониёров Алишер Худайбердиевич
Тошкент давлат шарқшунослик университети профессори,
Эшмухаматов Ахрор Шарипович
Тошкент давлат шарқшунослик университети
таянч докторанти.

Резюме: *Ушбу мақолада Жиззах воҳасининг табиий географик жойлашуви ҳамда чорвачилик билан шуғулланиш учун қулай иқлим шароитлари сабабли аҳолининг қадимдан ушбу соҳа билан шуғулланиб келганлиги ҳудудда олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар натижалари асосида ёритилган. Шунингдек воҳа аҳолисининг кундалик турмуш тарзида муҳим аҳамият касб этган чорва маҳсулотлари ва уларнинг турларини эъзозлаши натижасида вужудга келган кўплаб урф–одатлар, маросимлар,*

анъаналар ва ўзига хос касбий қадриятлар шаклланганлиги дала-этнографик матиреаллар асосида кўрсатиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: *Моргузар, Нурота, Мирзачўл, Фулбо, Сағаноқ, Беккелди, Қамиш, Пардақултепа, Комилбоботепа, Сайхонсой, Такатош, Сузмойилота, Фарн, Чўпон таёғи, Оқсоқ ота, Оқлик, “пода қўшиш”.*

ТРАДИЦИИ И ОБРЯДЫ ЖИВОТНОВОДСТВА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ДЖИЗАКСКОГО ОАЗИСА)

*т.ф.д. проф. Дониеров Алишер Худайбердиевич
профессор Ташкентского государственного университета
востоковедения,*

Эшмухаматов Ахрор Шарипович

*Базовый докторант Ташкентского государственного университета
востоковедения.*

Резюме: *Настоящая статья основана на результатах археологических исследований в Джизакском оазисе, издавна используемом населением благодаря своему естественно-географическому положению и благоприятным климатическим условиям для животноводства. Полевые этнографические материалы показывают также, что многие обычаи, обряды, традиции и специфические профессиональные ценности сформировались в результате бережного отношения к продуктам животноводства и их видам, имеющим важное значение в повседневной жизни людей оазиса.*

Ключевые слова: *Моргузар, Нурота, Мирзачул, Гульбо, Сағанок, Беккельди, Камыш, Пардакултепа, Комилбоботепа, Сайхонсай, Такатош, Сузмойлота, Фарн, Пастуший посох, Хромой отец, Белый, “присоединения стадо”.*

The economy of the peoples of Central Asia has long been shaped by natural geographical features, and due to the first division of labor that took place in the Bronze Age, it was divided into nomadic groups engaged in agriculture, settlement and animal husbandry. In the Jizzakh oasis, along with agriculture, there were favorable conditions for livestock. The convenience of pastures in terms of natural location, the abundance of various pastures and grasses for livestock allowed the sheep to multiply and fatten. Dozens of mountain valleys of the Morguzar ridge, the

foothills of Mount Nurata and the lowlands adjacent to Mirzachol have long been known for their grassy pastures.

The territory of the Jizzakh oasis consists of mountainous and foothill areas, which are very convenient for hunting and nomadic pastoral peoples. In this respect, these areas are rich in many archeological monuments inherited from ancient hunters and nomadic pastoralists. Archaeologists have also confirmed that our ancestors have been engaged in animal husbandry since ancient times through rock carvings left by them.

Scholars note that in ancient and early Middle Ages, Central Asia was inhabited by Turkic-Sarmatian, Yuechji, Hun, Usun, Eftal, Khioni, Kidari, Turkic and other tribes with different names that differed little from the peoples of the region in terms of language and way of life. Certain groups of them remained in the cattle-friendly areas of the Jizzakh oasis and continued to run their traditional farms. They searched for grassy pastures and settled mainly in the foothills, valley valleys of mountain rivers and streams, in areas not yet developed by local settlers and livestock [1.72–74]. Continuing the tradition of specialized farming, they were engaged not only in pastoralism, but also in simple farming.

As a result of field archeological research conducted by M.Khujanazarov, more than 1000 rock galleries were studied on the northern slopes of Morguzar Mountain, from the location of Takatosh in the Saykhansay gorge. They belong to several epochs, the oldest of which is said to date back to the Neolithic and Bronze Ages, and the latter to antiquity and the Middle Ages [2.22]. The rocks here depict hunting scenes, many wild and domestic animals, the performance of religious ceremonies, and more.

Specialists examined the Suzmoyilota rocks in the mountains and hills north of Jiligulli village of Sharof Rashidov district, the Nakhrajsay (Kattasay) gorge where Nakhraj village is located in Gallaorol district, the Yukorisay gorge above the Old Forish village of Forish district, and many new rock art monuments from the valleys have been registered and put into scientific circulation [3.54–57]. In addition, members of the expedition led by F.Akchaev in March-April 2021 in the territory of the villages Chubor and Sangzor of Bakhmal district of the Morguzar mountain range revealed hundreds of rock paintings. In these rock paintings, the wild animals are the species of animals that lived in the mountains and foothills in ancient and modern times, while the domestic animals are the ones that have been captured by humankind over these long periods of time.

Wild animals include primitive bull, primitive cow, mountain goat, argali, gazelle, saiga, original deer, wild horse, pendant, wild boar, as well as wild animals

such as lion, tiger, cheetah, leopard, wolf, fox, chihuahua and others. Images of snakes and birds are sometimes found on rocks [4.52]. Rare examples of this primitive and ancient art testify to the ancient roots of the livestock sector in the Jizzakh oasis.

Indeed, in the history of human society, animal husbandry was one of the most ancient forms of traditional farming and one of the main types of labor that determined the source of livelihood. Since ancient times, when the process of capturing and domesticating animals began, the rituals and customs associated with animal husbandry reflect the attitude of the people to the animal world. At the same time, they embody the relationship between man and nature, people and the animal kingdom, life experiences, spiritual views of human society related to several thousand years of labor activity.

In particular, fragments of a sheep's skull were found next to the objects in the Saganak cemetery studied by A.A. Gritsina [5.78]. Sheep bones were placed in the middle of the head of two corpses in the tomb of Gulbo, which was studied by FE Toshbaev in Zaamin district [6.43–45]. In the Shirinsay cemetery, studied by VF Gaydukevich, sheep bones were found in front of the pelvis, the head of the body [7.337]. In the tomb of 28 people in Shirinsoy, studied by VF Gaydukevich, in Bekkeldi and Qamish tombs, studied by FE Toshboev, ceramic palms with the image of a sheep (lamb) on the handle were studied. P.H.Pardaev also studied materials related to animal husbandry at the Pardaqlutepa and Komilbobotepa monuments in Jizzakh. There are statues of rams with twisted horns, about 10 pot bases with the symbol of a sheep's head. Archaeologist MH Pardaev, who studied the essence of these findings in a scientific analysis, states that they are "associated with nomadic pastoral peoples" [8.42-43].

It is noted that M.H.Pardaev buried a sheep's skull in the upper part of the grave (above the corpse bones) studied in Yoyilma mahalla of Sh.Rashidov district [9.261]. Evaluating such findings, M.H. Pardaev said that "the cult of the sheep should be sought not only in the spiritual culture of other regions, but also in the myths of the Turkic peoples associated with totemism. In fact, from the last quarter of the first millennium BC, the "Melon Culture" was formed in the middle reaches of the Syrdarya (ie, in the present-day Jizzakh oasis) and had a strong influence on neighboring agricultural oases. During the various Turkic dynasties (Sarmatians, Yuezhi, Huns, Hephthalites, and Turkish Khanates) that prevailed in Central Asia before the Arab conquest, sheep-herding was widespread in this area. gives [9.262].

Sources state that the Kanguys, who also controlled the Jizzakh oasis in ancient times, worshiped the Zoroastrian god Farn [10.6]. This god, the goddess Farn, was accepted as a sheep. The sheep bones found in the tombs, its symbol or the images of sheep in pottery indicate that sheep-breeding has a high position in the economy and spiritual world of the Jizzakh oasis, and is considered a symbol of abundance and blessing.

As mentioned above, as a result of respect for livestock by the people of the oasis, many customs, rituals, traditions and specific professional values associated with them have been formed, some of which can be seen today.

In particular, the shepherd has always been a constant companion and has been required to treat him with respect. It is usually forbidden to jump on a stick lying on the ground, pressing it. If he accidentally grabs it or jumps over it, he is lifted from the ground with both hands and kissed three times. Otherwise, the animal will get sick and die. According to the shepherds, a lot depends on the choice of a lucky stick, and the saying in one of the folk proverbs "from the bride's foot, from the shepherd's stick" also confirms the above idea.

All pets have separate patrons, most of whom are associated with Muslim saints. In particular, the piri of all shepherds was Hazrat Ishaq [11.71], the patron saint of the year was Kambar ota, the shepherd was the shepherd, the camel was Aysil Kara, the cattle was Zangiota, and the goat was Sajan [12.194–195]. The historian V.Sh. According to the legend, Zangi bobo was a patron of shepherds [13.163].

Another tradition associated with sheep-breeding is the ritual of purification before taking these sheep to spring and summer pastures. To do this, one of the shepherds went around the sheepfold with a torch in his hand, and before taking the sheep out of the sheepfold, incense was taken to protect it from humans and evil eyes. Before the owner of the herd took the sheep out to pasture, the god called the respectable people of the village and the mullah's blessings were dedicated to the shepherd Piri Choponota. When the sheep returned to the winter, they lit a fire in the middle of the barn, drove away the animals, and "cleaned" the cattle with incense.

Like sheep, the Jizzakh oasis farm also raises pigs for the market. The population was constantly monitoring the condition of the cattle, so a number of traditions related to the care of cattle have survived to this day. For example, when a cattle became ill, it was taken to a village shepherd. He used a shepherd's staff, a doppi (telpagi) or a turban to stroke the animal's stomach 3-4 times and recited a

prayer. If this did not help, they took Zangi's father to a place where he was "lame" and tried to correct him by turning him three times.

In the past, people believed in the evil eye. That is why newborn calves, slaves, calves, lambs are hidden from unfamiliar eyes. In particular, after two weeks in a barn, a rope was tied around his neck. Sometimes a black flat stone was pierced in the middle and hung around his neck to make a tumor out of it.

Some of the weapons in the livestock industry are also considered sacred. In particular, the head for tying the lambs, the yokes for tying the hooves and hooves, and the ring for catching the horse were not given to the stranger by the master. It is forbidden to carry women on ropes and weapons. The people believed in the sanctity of milk. They have formed various curses and oaths related to this product. "Let the white strike", "Let the white meet the valley" and others. As in many nations, the ban on milk is common among the population of the oasis. In particular, the myth that milk cannot be taken out of the house after sunset, especially on a starry night in the light of the moon, is still preserved.

It was believed that wolves and thieves would sometimes be protected if a sheep's arm bone was hung around a camel's neck. There are many legends among the people about the wonderful properties of these bones. In the past, in the Turkic-Mongol peoples, the sheep's tail was considered a mysterious property. The fortune tellers made various predictions based on it. There were a number of rituals associated with the disease of cattle. The herdsmen, who did not know the original cause of the disease, explained it by the fact that evil spirits clung to the flock. In particular, they sought to protect sheep herds from the diseases of the Siberian, Yazvasi, and Moths by turning them around the tombs of the saints and sacrificing them. In the imagination of the population, black cats were considered to have an unknown, mysterious power. Therefore, cats of this color were secretly killed by their owners and their bodies were placed on the neighbor, thereby driving away the evil forces. Sometimes a human skull from an old tomb was placed inside the coffin. Spruce branches and incense were burned to ward off evil spirits through fire.

The mentioned customs and rituals, as in many other cattle-breeding Turkic tribes, are reminiscent of religious rituals associated with various manifestations of pre-Islamic Shamanism (ancestral spirit, Blue God, rivers, water bodies, etc.). In the Turkestan (Morguzar) mountains of the oasis, in the Uriklisay gorge, there is a huge (5x 3m) shaman-stone god (Tangri sang) facing east (sunrise) from the cliff [14.3215–3224]. imaginations and traditions are widespread.

In addition, we can see that the oasis in the oasis combines many of the above-mentioned traditions. This ceremony is mainly typical of the mountainous areas of Zaamin, Bakhmal and Sh. Rashidov districts of the oasis. carried out. During the ceremony, the seeds that live in the village are slaughtered and the sheep are sacrificed in turn (the kinship community comes in turn once every few years). It will be attended by one elderly representative from each household of the village. At this ceremony, who will be the shepherd this year, the amount of money paid to the shepherd for each head of livestock (horses, cattle, sheep and goats) or its substitute natural product (wheat, barley or cattle), the requirements for shepherds are agreed. is obtained.

The ceremony is held at the shrines, and the reason for this is that, firstly, the status of the shrines in society is taken into account, and the blessings of the animals are to protect them from disease. and compliance will depend on the conscience of the parties. Therefore, there is a sense of fear among the population of the magical properties of the shrines, believing that religious rules such as not lying there remind the parties of their spiritual duty [15]. Furthermore, the shrines are a sacred place that belongs neither to the state nor to a particular person, and according to popular belief, any agreement made in this area will have a divine significance. Therefore, since a verbal covenant is a sacred covenant, breaking it is equated with a grave sin.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of traditional animal husbandry today combines centuries-old religious and mythological worldview, ethno-national and regional traditions. Rock paintings and unique archeological finds from the oasis prove that animal husbandry was one of the oldest forms of traditional farming and the main source of livelihood in the history of human society. At the same time, since the beginning of the process of capturing and domesticating animals, various traditions and customs related to animal husbandry have been formed, and people's attitude to the animal world has been formed. With the passage of time and the development of human society, popular views have been formed, which are aimed at protecting livestock, which is their main economic source, from various calamities, and which can be seen to this day.

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